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**ENTREPRENEURSHIP SKILLS REQUIRED BY CONSTRUCTION TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION
STUDENTS IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS OF NIGERIA**

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Abstract

This study was undertaken with the aim to determine entrepreneurship skills required by CTE students at the undergraduate level of tertiary institutions of Nigeria. 2 research questions were asked to guide the conduct of this study. The study was conducted in the North Western part of Nigeria involving tertiary institutions that offer CTE at the undergraduate level. A survey research design was employed for the study. The population of the study comprised all 300 level CTE students in 3 tertiary institutions offering CTE in NW Nigeria. Simple random sampling technique was used to sample 186 CTE students from a population of 367. The instrument used for data collection is a structured questionnaire validate by 3 experts. Cronbach's Alpha reliability used to determine the reliability coefficient of the instrument which stood at 0.82. Data for the study was analysed using the mean and standard deviation. Findings from the result of the study revealed, business planning skills, management skills among the entrepreneurship skills required by CTE students in tertiary institutions of Nigeria. The findings also revealed the need for curriculum restructuring to incorporate entrepreneurship skills, among the appropriate approaches for enhancing CTE students' entrepreneurship skills. Finally, the study recommends that the government should provide the necessary facilities for effective entrepreneurship skills acquisition by CTE students in tertiary institutions of Nigeria.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship skills, Construction Technology Education, Tertiary Institutions

Introduction

Construction Technology Education (CTE) is a course under Vocational Technical and Education (VTE) offered at the under graduate level in tertiary institutions of Nigeria which focus on training students to acquire the relevant skills for employment after graduation. Tertiary institutions offering CTE in Nigeria include Universities, Polytechnics and Colleges of Education (COE) (Isa, et al.,2022). Accordingly, CTE as a course under VTE offered at the undergraduate level of tertiary institutions of Nigeria is usually within the duration of 4 to 5 sessions or four to five years in the universities, and affiliate institutions like the polytechnic and COE (Isa et al., 2022). Additionally, CTE at tertiary institutions encompasses building and wood technology education which focus on application of theoretical and practical skills of building and woodworking (Mshelia, 2012). Further, CTE as a course in tertiary institutions afford students with the skills of designing and erecting various building and wooden structures (Fauzi, Ali, & Amirudin, 2019). Similarly, the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2016) in

the revised curriculum of CTE program for undergraduate level amply stated that CTE programs offers students with the skills to work in the industry as well as in the private sector of the economy. Essentially, CTE at tertiary institutions of Nigeria aims towards producing competent and efficient personnel for the industrial and private sectors of the economy. Moreover, the FRN (2016) stated the object of CTE program at the undergraduate level of tertiary institutions to include; Provide a course of instruction in CTE for the pursuit and acquisition of learning and knowledge for service to humanity; Provide sound foundation for interested graduates to pursue higher degree in CTE; Equip service teachers with pedagogical and practical skills; Develop soft skills (Positive values and attitudes)for efficient discharge of their duties; And to develop the spirit of self-reliance and entrepreneurship among CTE students. However, it is obvious that CTE at tertiary institution pay much emphasis on enhancing CTE students' ability and entrepreneurship.

Entrepreneurship is the process of creating and developing economic activities through creativity, innovation, and risk taking in businesses in an organisation(Sousa, 2018). Accordingly, Badawi, et al., (2019) described entrepreneurship as the practice of starting a new organisation or venture with the soul aim of generating business potentials for success in businesses. Essentially, entrepreneurship focus on starting and operating a business in an organisation through the application of entrepreneurial rudiments. However, to achieve a successful entrepreneurship, acquiring entrepreneurship skills has become inevitable.

Entrepreneurship skills are skills required by an individual for pursuing investment prospects, as well as establishing and successfully running a business enterprise (Bala, Kareem, Hassan, & Nwankwo, 2020). Equally, Shuaibu and Kamin (2019) described entrepreneurship skill as skill required by an organisation or individual for starting, operating, and sustaining a business within the limit of a market where prospects for exploration exist. Accordingly, Sousa (2018) perceives entrepreneurship skills as the skills for identifying opportunities and creating new businesses. Additionally, entrepreneurship skills entails skills needed for risk taking in business and advancement in an enterprise (Badawi et al., 2019). Further, Ojo (2016) Defined entrepreneurship skills as skills that aid an individual in identifying business opportunities, take advantage of scarce resources, control and coordinate available human and material resources in an enterprise. Entrepreneurship skills in essence, could be seen as skills for operating and progressing in a business. Furthermore, various entrepreneurship skills required for a successful business operation are identified by authors. In this sense, Eunice Abdul (2018) identified interpersonal skills, management skills, and ICT skills as skills needed for successful business venture. In the same vein, Bala et al. (2020); Ojo ; Shuaibu and Kamin (2019)listed business planning skills, financial management skills, management skills, ICT skills self-motivational skills, communication skills and marketing skills as components of entrepreneurship skills needed for successes in business.

However, despite the significant role entrepreneurship skills play in helping individuals manage and succeed in a business enterprise, its elements have not been incorporated into the curriculum of CTE at the undergraduate level of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. In this regard, Isa et.al. (2022) stated that the curriculum of CTE at the undergraduate level of tertiary institutions in Nigeria primarily focus on entrepreneurship concepts and philosophy without emphases on entrepreneurship skills acquisition, a situation that resulted to CTE students graduating without the needed entrepreneurship skills for business operation. Similarly, Bala et al. (2020) remarked that CTE students failed to succeed in business venture after graduation due to their lack of skills in managing businesses, wrong decision taken, lack of knowledge on financial management and marketing skills. The author further stated that all this boils down to the curriculum which does not reflect these skills as components of entrepreneurship needed to be inculcated to the students. Equally, employers in construction industries,

specifically building and wood construction industries in Nigeria have shown neglect on employing graduates of CTE due to their inability to exhibit entrepreneurship competencies (Olabiyi, 2014). Unfortunately, this situation has resulted to increase in high rate of unemployment among graduates of CTE in Nigeria. Regrettably, this high rate of unemployment rate has resulted to CTE graduates' indulgence in ill vices like thuggery and banditry (Olabiyi, 2015). In this regard, there is urgent need to inculcate the required entrepreneurship skills to CTE students in order to curtail the problems of unemployment among CTE graduates. However, despite the problems of CTE graduates' deficiency in entrepreneurship skills, studies relating to entrepreneurship skills in CTE have being inadequate. Therefore, there is the need to undertake a study in order to identify entrepreneurship skills required by CTE students in Nigeria tertiary institutions, hence the need for this study.

Purpose of the Study

1. To determine elements of entrepreneurship skills required by CTE students in tertiary institutions of Nigeria
2. To identify appropriate approaches for enhancing entrepreneurship skills of CTE students in tertiary institutions of Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were asked to guide the conduct of this study:

1. What are the elements of entrepreneurship skills required by CTE students in tertiary institutions of Nigeria?
2. What are the appropriate approaches for enhancing CTE students' entrepreneurship skills in tertiary institutions of Nigeria?

Methodology

Methodology entails procedures involved in conducting a research. In this sense, the methodology for this study is discussed under the following subheadings:

a. Research Design

This study employed a survey research design. A survey research design are set of procedures in which investigators administer a survey to a sample or to entire population of people to describe the attitude, perception, opinion, and behaviours or characteristics of the population (Creswell & Hirose, 2019). The survey research design is most appropriate for this study because it will help in eliciting responses of the respondents on their opinion on elements of entrepreneurship skills required by CTE students.

b. Study Area

The study is conducted in the north western states of Nigerian involving tertiary institutions offering CTE at the undergraduate levels. The tertiary institutions include Bayero University Kano, Kaduna Polytechnic, and Federal College of education (Technical) Bichi, Kano state.

c. Population and Sample

The population for this study comprised 300 level students of CTE in the 3 tertiary institutions offering CTE in North western states of Nigeria. The population for this research comprised 367. Furthermore, simple random sampling technique was used in this study to select 186 respondents from the population using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table of sample size determination from a known population. According to the authors, a total of 186 sample can represent a population of 367. In this regard, the number of respondents from each institution was dependent on the size of the sample. Therefore, more sampling was allocated to institutions with much respondents, and less to fewer respondents. However, in order to give each

respondent an equal chance of been selected, every respondent was assigned a number, and selected using a random number generator. Table I illustrate the population and sample for this study

Table I: Population and Sample of Respondents

Institution	Population	Sample
Bayero University Kano	135	66
Federal College of Education Technical Bichi, Kano	120	62
Kaduna Polytechnic	112	58
Total	367	186

d. Instrumentation

The instrument used for data collection in this study is a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher. The questionnaire contains 43 item statement with a 5-point Likert scale response options. The response option of the questionnaire is in two categories; first is to answer research question1 on elements of entrepreneurship skills required by CTE students with options as Very Highly Required (VHR)5; Highly Required (HR)4; Moderately Required (ML)3; Slightly Required (SR)2; Not Required (NR)1. The second response option is to answer research question 2 with options as Highly Appropriate (HA)5; Moderately Appropriate (MA)4; Slightly Appropriate (SA)3; Inappropriate (I)2; Highly Inappropriate (HI)1.

e. Validity and Reliability

The structured questionnaire used in this research was validated by 3 experts, one in the field of TVE, one in the field of CTE, and one in entrepreneurship. Subsequently, the final draft of the questionnaire was developed based on the observations and suggestions made by the validates. Similarly, in order to ascertain the reliability of the questionnaire, a pilot study was undertaken in COE Gidan Waya Kaduna State. Data from the pilot study was analysed using IBM SPSS version 24 to process the Cronbach’s Alfa reliability. Further, the reliability coefficient of the instrument stood at 0.82 indicating a high reliability coefficient.

f. Analyses Technique

Data from this study was analysed using Mean, and standard deviation through IBM SPSS Version 24. The results of the analysis are presented in tables II and III. Further, items with mean responses of 3.50 and above were considered Required (R) or Appropriate (A), while items with mean values below 3.50 were considered Not Required (NR) or Inappropriate (I).

Results and Discussion

The result of the study is presented in tables II and III

RQ1 What are the elements of entrepreneurship skills required by CTE students in tertiary institutions of Nigeria?

Table II: Mean and Standard Deviation of responses on the Elements of Entrepreneurship Skills Required by CTE Students

S/n	Statements	Mean	SD	Remark
Business Planning Skills				
1	Ability to outline specific business goals to achieve	4.34	.75	Required
2	Ability to develop a work plan for project execution	4.32	.78	Required
3	Ability to identify location for setting up business	3.93	1.16	Required
4	Ability to plan cutting list for project execution	4.14	.86	Required
5	Ability to plan bill of materials for projects	4.24	.79	Required
6	Ability to plan strategies for marketing products	4.17	.90	Required
7	Ability to plan strategies for distribution of finished products	4.18	.82	Required
Marketing Skills				
8	Ability to conduct market survey on products	4.29	.83	Required
9	Ability to advertise products using media sources	4.35	.73	Required
10	Ability to keep inventory/record of products	4.19	.79	Required
11	Ability to showcase products in trade fare and other product exhibition fares	3.94	1.06	Required
12	Ability to explore business opportunities	3.74	1.25	Required
ICT Skills				
13	Ability to use the computer software to prepare cutting list for a project	3.66	1.49	Required
14	Ability to use computer aided instruction in preparing bill of material for a project	4.27	.74	Required
15	Ability to use computer software in designing projects	4.37	.84	Required
16	Ability to use the internet in advertising and marketing products	4.04	1.03	Required
17	Ability to use the internet to keep abreast with advancement in products	4.1774	.81	Required
Management Skills				
18	Ability to manage human and material resources to meet organisational goals	4.26	.75	Required
19	Ability to set standards on attaining business objectives	4.14	.90	Required
20	Ability to set effective communication channel for feed-back from customers	4.29	.72	Required
21	Ability to manage time in meeting customers demand	4.16	.80	Required
22	Ability to create conducive work environment	4.41	.69	Required
23	Ability to implement organisational policies	4.31	.77	Required
Financial Management Skills				
24	Ability to take risks in business	4.26	.70	Required
25	Ability to prepare financial statements	4.22	.84	Required
26	Ability to prepare budget for project execution	4.26	.71	Required
27	Ability to source funds for project execution	4.37	.66	Required
28	Ability to identify cost implication for projects	4.17	1.16	Required
Interpersonal Skills				
29	Ability to foster team work with subordinates	4.27	1.09	Required
30	Ability to accept criticism and opinion of subordinates	4.14	1.02	Required
31	Ability to relate with customers in a friendly manner	4.22	.87	Required
32	Ability to deal with difficult costumers with patience	4.36	.76	Required
33	Ability to fulfil agreement with costumers	4.25	.81	Required

As presented in Table II, result of the overall data distribution on elements of entrepreneurship skills required by CTE students in tertiary institutions of Nigeria revealed that all the 33 items have their mean values above 3.50 indicating that the respondents opined to all items as elements of entrepreneurship skills required by CTE students.

RQ2 What are the appropriate approaches for enhancing CTE students’ entrepreneurship skills in tertiary institutions of Nigeria?

Table III: Mean and Standard Deviation of responses on Appropriate Approaches for Enhancing CTE students Entrepreneurship Skills.

S/n	Statements	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Curriculum restructure	4.17	.84	Appropriate
2	Provision of adequate facilities	4.31	.75	Appropriate
3	Engagement in assignments on entrepreneurship skills	4.11	.88	Appropriate
4	Regular organisation of briefings for students	4.23	.84	Appropriate
5	Engagement in project planning activities	4.05	.93	Appropriate
6	Grouping students on project activities	4.31	.81	Appropriate
7	Engagement on project presentation	4.25	.85	Appropriate
8	Engagement in application of computer software in project design	3.98	.91	Appropriate
9	Application of intermate to explore marketing strategies	4.29	.79	Appropriate
10	Application of scrabs in project activities	3.91	1.03	Appropriate

As presented in Table III, the overall data distribution on appropriate approaches for enhancing CTE students’ entrepreneurship skills in tertiary institutions of Nigeria revealed that all the 10 items have their mean values above 3.50 indicating that the respondents opined to all items as appropriate approaches for enhancing CTE students’ entrepreneurship skills.

Discussion of Findings

Findings from the result of the study with respect to research question one revealed that business planning skills, marketing skills, ICT skills, management skills, financial management skills, and interpersonal skills as entrepreneurship skills elements required by CTE students in tertiary institutions of Nigeria. This finding is in accordance with Bala et al. (2020); Olabiyi (2014); Undiyaundeye and Otu (2015) who stated that ICT skills, marketing skills are entrepreneurship skills that students should possess because of the trends in modern work environment. The authors further added that inculcating these entrepreneurship skills to students will assist in curbing the problem of unemployment among graduates. Similarly, Ojo (2016); Shuaibu and Kamin (2019) listed business planning skills, management skills, financial management skills, and interpersonal skills as skills essential for students to be acquainted with before graduation.

Findings of research question two on appropriate approaches for enhancing CTE students’ entrepreneurship skills revealed restructuring the curriculum of CTE to incorporate elements of entrepreneurship skills as appropriate approach for enhancing CTE students’ entrepreneurship skills. This result has implication for CTE curriculum planners, as the findings could serve as a guide for CTE curriculum planners in restructuring the existing curriculum by identifying appropriate elements of entrepreneurship skill required for incorporation into CTE program at the under graduate level. This finding is in line with the view of Akhmetshin et al. (2019) who stated that entrepreneurship skills are desirable for students to learn in schools, and in order for its teaching to be successful, the curriculum must contain elements of entrepreneurship skills. Findings also revealed provision of adequate facilities, organising briefing, engagement in project activities that involve using computer and software, group presentation as approaches appropriate for entrepreneurship skills of CTE students. The implication of this finding is directly to the government at all levels in ensuring appropriate and adequate provision of the facilities for effective entrepreneurship skills acquisition. This is in line with the views of Badawi et al. (2019); Pardo-Garcia

and Barac (2020) that computers, internet and other facilities are essential for students activities especially when grouped to investigate and make presentations on outcomes that enhance students' entrepreneurship skills. Further findings of the result also revealed engaging students with activities that will foster students' acquisition of project planning activities. This result has implication for CTE lecturers and students as lecturers will employ instructional approaches like project method in teaching students, also CTE students will directly be involved in project activities that will enhance their entrepreneurship skills. In support of this finding Eunice Abdul (2018): Isa et.al (2023) stated that entrepreneurship skills are vital, and for individuals' to acquire the skills there is every need to teach students procedures to plan strategies for achieving a successful business venture, especially when planning project execution.

From the findings of this study, it is can be deduced that acquiring entrepreneurship skills is vital for the success of CTE students in employment sustainability. Therefore, instilling the relevant entrepreneurship skills and adopting appropriate strategies for enhancing entrepreneurship skills of CTE students identified in this study is desirable for tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Conclusion

Entrepreneurship skill has been found to be skills needed for effective participation at world of work in this 21st century era. Unfortunately, many CTE students in Nigeria graduate without acquiring these skills. In this regard, this study was undertaken to investigate elements of entrepreneurship skills required by CTE students, and appropriate approaches for enhancing CTE students' entrepreneurship skills in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Findings from this study revealed that ICT, business planning, management, financial management, interpersonal, marketing, and interpersonal skills as entrepreneurship skills CTE students required. The findings also identified curriculum restructure, organising briefings on entrepreneurship skills for students by institutions in collaboration with entrepreneurship organisations as part of appropriate approaches for enhancing CTE students' entrepreneurship skills.

Recommendation

This study recommends the following as appropriate for CTE students to acquire entrepreneurship skills effectively;

1. Government should restructure the existing curriculum of CTE at the undergraduate level to incorporate entrepreneurship skills elements to enhance CTE students' entrepreneurship skills.
2. Government should also provide adequate facilities like computers, free internet services including equipment and materials for project execution, this will go a long way in improving entrepreneurship skills of CTE students.

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